

Current DNA Analyzing Techniques and Application in Genetic Research in Sri Lanka: A Review

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Introduction

Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) is the genetic material that determines the traits of living organisms. With the development of new technologies, it has become possible to analyze DNA in increasingly sophisticated ways. In Sri Lanka, genetic research has been rapidly advancing, with the implementation of various DNA analyzing techniques. In this article, we will discuss the current DNA analyzing techniques and their applications in genetic research in Sri Lanka.

1. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR): PCR is a widely used technique to amplify a specific segment of DNA. PCR can replicate a small fragment of DNA millions of times, allowing researchers to obtain sufficient quantities of DNA for further analysis. PCR has been used in Sri Lanka to detect genetic mutations associated with diseases such as sickle cell anemia and thalassemia (Dissanayake & De Silva, 2016).
2. Real-time PCR: Real-time PCR is a variant of PCR that allows for the detection of DNA in real-time as it is amplified. Real-time PCR is used in Sri Lanka to detect infectious diseases such as dengue and tuberculosis (Fernando et al., 2018).
3. Next-generation sequencing (NGS): NGS is a high-throughput technique used to determine the DNA sequence of an entire genome. NGS can identify genetic mutations and structural variations that contribute to various diseases. NGS has been used in Sri Lanka to study genetic causes of cancer and rare diseases (Thiyagaraja & De Silva, 2017).
4. Forensic DNA Analysis: Forensic DNA analysis is used in Sri Lanka for criminal investigations and identifying missing persons. Short Tandem Repeat (STR) analysis is the most commonly used method for forensic DNA analysis in Sri Lanka (Samarasekera et al., 2018).

Conclusion

The use of various DNA analyzing techniques has significantly advanced genetic research in Sri Lanka. PCR, real-time PCR, NGS, and forensic DNA analysis are just a few examples of the innovative tools that have been developed to study DNA. The use of these techniques has allowed for a better understanding of the genetic basis of diseases and the development of potential treatments. Further research in DNA analysis will continue to drive medical and scientific advancements in Sri Lanka and beyond.

References:

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